

16 **Abstract**

17 The use of fecal indicators such as *Escherichia coli* has been proposed as a potential tool
18 to characterize microbial contamination of irrigation water. Recently, not only the type
19 of microbial indicator but also the methodologies used for enumeration have been called
20 into question. The goal of this study was to assess the microbial quality of different water
21 sources for irrigation of zucchini plants by using *E. coli* as an indicator of fecal
22 contamination and the occurrence of foodborne pathogens. Three water sources were
23 evaluated including reclaimed secondary treated water (RW-2), reclaimed tertiary UV-C
24 treated water (RW-3) and surface water (SW). The suitability of two *E. coli* quantification
25 techniques (plate count and qPCR) was examined for irrigation water and fresh produce.
26 *E. coli* levels using qPCR assay were significantly higher than that obtained by plate count
27 in all samples of irrigation water and fresh produce. The microbial quality of water
28 samples from RW-2 was well predicted by qPCR, as the presence of foodborne pathogens
29 were positively correlated with high *E. coli* levels. However, differences in the water
30 characteristics because of the water treatments influenced the suitability of qPCR as a
31 tool to predict potential contamination in irrigation water because no significant
32 differences were obtained between the number of cells of *E. coli* from RW-2 and RW-3,
33 probably due to the fact that qPCR assay cannot distinguish between viable and dead
34 cells. These results indicated that the selection of the most suitable technique for
35 enumeration of indicator microorganisms able to predict potential presence of fecal
36 contamination might be influenced by the water characteristic.

37

38 *Key words:* Fresh produce, qPCR, indicator microorganism, plate count, foodborne
39 pathogens, surface water, reclaimed water.

40

41 **Introduction**

42 Irrigation water is well recognized as one of the main risk factors for
43 contamination with pathogenic microorganism of fresh produce during the primary
44 production (EFSA, 2014). Different water sources can be used for primary production
45 depending on water availability and quality. Surface water seems to be the most
46 predominant water source for irrigation in many countries (Uyttendaele et al., 2015;
47 Allende and Monaghan et al., 2015). However, reclaimed water is being increasingly used
48 in arid and semi-arid zones around the world due to scarcity of other water sources
49 (Pachepsky et al., 2011). Among all types of water, surface and reclaimed water have
50 been classified as the most risky irrigation water sources (Ceuppens et al., 2015). To
51 promote produce safety, periodical water tests and monitoring of water sources have been
52 recommended as preventive measures for most of the Good Agricultural Practices (GAP)
53 guidelines.

54 The investigation of microbial indicators have been proposed as a good strategy
55 to characterize microbial contamination in water mostly due to the low prevalence of
56 foodborne pathogens as well as the high cost and time consumption of pathogen detection
57 (Ferguson et al., 2012). Currently, generic *Escherichia coli* seem to be the best indicator
58 bacteria able to identify fecal contamination when compared with the rest of microbial
59 indicators for irrigation water (Uyttendaele et al., 2015; Ceuppens et al., 2015). Research
60 focused on systematic longitudinal samplings demonstrated that presence of *E. coli*
61 provides evidence of an increased likelihood of potential contamination by ecologically
62 closely related pathogens such as pathogenic *E. coli* and *Salmonella*. (Ogden et al., 2001;
63 Harwood et al., 2005; Wilkes et al., 2009; EFSA et al., 2014; Holvoet et al., 2014;
64 Ceuppens et al., 2014; 2015; Castro-Ibañez et al., 2015a; 2015b). However, other studies
65 did not find a good correlation between levels of *E. coli* and prevalence of pathogenic

66 microorganisms, questioning the value of *E. coli* as a good indicator microorganism
67 (Benjamin et al., 2013; Pachepsky et al., 2014; Orlofsky et al., 2016). The reported
68 differences between previously published research papers could be due to discrepancies
69 on the sampling size and enumeration techniques.

70 Currently, only traditional culture techniques are used to enumerate *E. coli*
71 numbers in environmental samples, including irrigation water. However, qPCR method
72 to detect and enumerate *E. coli* in environmental samples has been reported as more
73 sensitive, reproducible and faster than plate counts. (Ahmed et al., 2012; Silva and
74 Domingues et al., 2015)). Ferguson et al., (2013) reported that a qPCR-based *E. coli* assay
75 was the best indicator for bacterial pathogens in water samples. Based on these reports,
76 there is a need to determine the most suitable techniques for quantification of *E. coli* and
77 its ability to distinguish the microbial quality of different irrigation water sources.

78 The goal of this study was to determine the most suitable techniques to quantify
79 generic *E. coli* in irrigation water and fresh produce samples and their ability to predict
80 the occurrence of foodborne pathogens. Two selected enumeration methods, plate count
81 and qPCR, were subsequently used to evaluate the microbial quality of different irrigation
82 water sources based on their *E. coli* levels and foodborne pathogen prevalence.

83

84 **1. Materials and methods**

85 *1.1. Experimental design*

86 Zucchini plants (*Cucurbita pepo* L.) were grown under hydroponic system
87 (Coconut fibre; Pelemix, Alhama de Murcia, Spain) in a greenhouse located next to the
88 wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) (Roldán-Balsicas, Murcia, Spain) from December
89 2014 until March 2015. Irrigation water obtained from the WWTP was subjected to a
90 secondary treatment, using an extended aeration system (reactor + clarifier system),

91 followed by a tertiary treatment with an ultraviolet-C (UV-C) disinfection system. Three
92 types of water were used for irrigation: surface water (SW), reclaimed water obtained
93 from the WWTP after a secondary treatment (RW-2) and reclaimed water obtained from
94 the WWTP after a tertiary treatment (RW-3). Surface water and reclaimed water from
95 the secondary treatment plant were obtained as previously described ([López-Galvez et
96 al., 2014](#)). Briefly, Reclaimed water (RW-2) was obtained after a secondary treatment
97 using an extended aeration system (reactor + clarifier system). Reclaimed water (RW-3)
98 was obtained from the tertiary treatment plant after treating RW-2, including coagulation-
99 flocculation and complementary lamellar clarification, followed by filtration on an open
100 sand bed filter and disinfection using a UV-C light treatment. The UV disinfection system
101 is based on two lamp modules (8 lamps each module). Lamps are a 254 nm high intensity
102 amalgam (SLR32143 HP, WEDECO, USA). All types of irrigation water were
103 supplemented with fertilizer solutions as needed based on commercial practices for
104 hydroponic production of zucchini plants. Three replicates of 15 plants (n=45) were
105 grown per treatment.

106

107 *1.2. Sample collection*

108 Water samples were collected in duplicate twice per week between January-March
109 2015 (n = 108). One liter of each type of water was collected using sterile polypropylene
110 plastic bottles. Samples were transported to the laboratory (30 min) and stored at 4 °C for
111 16 h maximum before processing. Additionally, each sampling day, 10 L of each water
112 source was passed through Modified Moore Swabs (MMS) by means of a peristaltic pump
113 as previously described by [Sbodio et al., \(2013\)](#).

114 Zucchini samples (n=135) were taken weekly during the harvest period January-
115 March 2015 that corresponded to 9 weeks. Each sampling day, 5 zucchini samples of

116 similar maturity stage were harvested from plants irrigated with each type of irrigation
117 water. Zucchini samples were randomly picked from the plants and aseptically transferred
118 into sterile bags.

119

120 1.3. *Cultivation and molecular-based E. coli quantification*

121 Cultivation-based enumeration of *E. coli* in irrigation water (n=108) and zucchini
122 (n=135) samples was performed as previously described in [López-Gálvez et al. \(2014\)](#).

123 For *E. coli* qPCR quantification in each type of water, two samples (250 ml) were
124 further pooled in one sample (n=54) at each sampling day. This pool (500 mL) was
125 filtered through 0.45 µm pore size nitrocellulose membranes. The filters were kept at -80
126 °C until the genomic DNA extraction was performed. For zucchini, 3 samples per
127 treatment and sampling day (n=81) were taken. Buffered peptone water (BPW, AES
128 Chemunex, Marcy l'Etoile, France) was used to homogenize the zucchini samples. The
129 homogenate was centrifuged at 3000 g for 10 min and the obtained pellet kept at -80 °C
130 until the genomic DNA was performed.

131

132 1.4. *DNA extraction*

133 Bacterial community from irrigation water was recovered from membrane filters
134 as follows. Each membrane was washed off with 20 mL of a 0.01% PBS-Tween80
135 solution. The obtained bacterial cell suspension was pelleted by centrifugation at 3070 g
136 during 10 min. DNA extraction of the pellet was performed using a commercial kit as
137 previously described ([Truchado et al., 2016](#)). In the case of zucchini, genomic DNA from
138 the previously obtained pellet was isolated using E.Z.N.A.[®] Genomic DNA Isolation Kits
139 (Omega Bio-Tek, Norcross, USA).

140

141 1.5. *qPCR procedure*

142 Quantitative PCR was performed using an ABI 7500 Sequence Detection System
143 (ABI, Applied Biosystems, Madrid, Spain). Primers and probes for detecting genes of *E.*
144 *coli* 23S rRNA as well as the applied cycling parameters were as previously described
145 (Knappett et al., 2011). Amplification and detection were carried out in 96-well plates
146 using KAPA PROBE FAST Universal qPCR Master mix kit (KapaBiosystems,
147 Massachusetts, USA). Each reaction was run in triplicate containing 5 µL of DNA
148 template. A non-template control (NTC) was included. Standard curves were made using
149 known concentrations of genomic DNA isolated from *E. coli* CECT 5945. The *E. coli*
150 concentration in the stock solution was verified by plating on plate count agar (PCA;
151 Oxoid, Hampshire, UK).

152

153 1.6. *Pathogenic microorganisms*

154 Presence or absence of *E. coli* O157:H7, STEC (Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli*)
155 and *Salmonella* spp. were determined in water and zucchini samples. Water samples
156 (n=54) were polled as was previously indicated. Zucchini samples were polled per
157 treatment and sampling day (n=27)) The MMS previously obtained after filtering 10 L of
158 water were placed in a stomacher bag containing 200 mL of 40% BPW and incubated at
159 37 °C for 18–20 h. For zucchini samples, about 160 mL of the BPW homogenate obtained
160 as previously described were incubated at 37 °C for 18± 2 h. Enriched samples were
161 supplemented with 30% glycerol and maintained at –20 °C until further analysis.
162 Prevalence of pathogenic microorganisms in water and zucchini samples was performed
163 using a Genedisc Cyclor multiplex PCR (Pall® Corporation, WA, USA) (Castro-Ibañez
164 et al., 2015b). The presumptive positive samples detected by the multiplex PCR were
165 cultured and confirmed in selective culture media (Holvoet et al., 2014; Castro-Ibañez et

166 al., 2015b). When needed, additional confirmation of presumptive *Salmonella* spp.
167 colonies was performed using a PCR System (Applied Biosystems, Madrid, Spain) (Al-
168 Moghazy et al., 2014).

169

170 1.7. 16S rRNA gene sequencing analysis of pathogenic strains

171 Suspected positive strains of *Salmonella*, *E. coli* O157:H7 and STEC obtained
172 from the multiplex PCR and culture isolation were further confirmed using 16S rRNA
173 sequencing analysis (Truchado et al., 2015). All sequences were subjected to BLAST
174 search (<http://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>) to determine the closest known taxon and
175 aligned using the Clustal Omega program (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalo/>).
176 To determine the taxonomy of each suspected *E. coli* strain, a 99% or higher match
177 between the sequence obtained (~ 800 bp) and the GenBank data was considered to
178 represent identity.

179

180 1.8. Statistical analysis

181 Calculation and graphical representation of the median and interquartile range
182 (IQR) of microbial counts were performed using Sigma Plot 12.5 Systat Software, Inc.
183 (Addilink Software Scientific, S.L. Barcelona). *E. coli* levels, determined by plate count
184 and qPCR assay, were log₁₀ transformed. IBM SPSS Statistics 19 was used for statistical
185 analysis. Except when stated otherwise, *P* values below 0.05 were considered statistically
186 significant. Shapiro-Wilk test was performed to assess the normality of the data (*P*>0.05).
187 Mann Whitney U and Kruskal–Wallis tests were used to examine the significant
188 differences between *E. coli* levels and the presence/absence of pathogens. The Pearson's
189 correlation coefficient (*r* value) was calculated to determine the correlation between data

190 obtained using plate count and qPCR assay. The significance was determined at the 95%
191 confidence level.

192

193 **2. Results**

194

195 2.1. *Suitability of different E. coli quantification techniques to predict fecal* 196 *contamination*

197 In all water samples, counts of cultivable *E. coli* were significantly lower than the
198 levels of the qPCR *E. coli* (**Fig. 1A**). In the case of zucchini, *E. coli* levels obtained by
199 using the plate count method were always below the detection limit (≤ 0.7 log cfu/g) while
200 qPCR *E. coli* levels were always above the detection limit (≤ 0.8 cells cfu/g) with a
201 median count of 2.64 log cells/g (IQR 2.46-3.05) (**Fig. 1B**). A strong correlation was
202 observed between both enumeration methods ($r=0.72$; $P<0.01$) ($n= 81$) (**Fig. 2**). In order
203 to determine the potential correlation between *E. coli* levels and the prevalence of enteric
204 foodborne pathogens, a multiplex PCR was performed (**Table 1**). Among the tested water
205 samples, 24.1% was positive for at least one bacterial pathogen, including 6 samples for
206 *Salmonella* spp., 4 samples for *E. coli* O157:H7 and 3 samples for non-O157:H7 STEC
207 strains. In the case of zucchini, only one sample was positive for *Salmonella* spp. by
208 multiplex PCR. When confirmation of the presumptive positive samples was performed,
209 none of the multiplex PCR positives for *Salmonella* spp. was confirmed by culture media
210 or *inv* gene amplification by PCR assay. In the case of *E. coli* O157:H7, only one
211 presumptive positive sample was confirmed by culture media and latex agglutination test.
212 To further characterize the isolated strain, 16S rRNA gene sequencing analysis was
213 carried out. The sequencing results showed resemblance to *E. coli* O157:H7 strain
214 WS4202 (99% similarity). Presumptive positives of non-O157:H7 STEC strains were

215 isolated by selective media and further characterized by 16S rRNA gene sequencing
216 analysis. Sequence similarity analysis was listed in the **Table 2**. Two isolated strains were
217 similar to STEC O104:H4 and another strain were similar to STEC O78 (99% similarity).

218 In order to determine the most suitable *E. coli* quantification method, the levels of
219 *E. coli* obtained by plate count and qPCR in positive and negative samples for the
220 presence of pathogenic bacteria were compared. Based on the obtained results, positives
221 samples for pathogenic bacteria showed significantly higher *E. coli* levels than samples
222 negative for the presence of foodborne pathogens when both enumeration methods were
223 used (**Fig. 3**). This indicates that both enumeration techniques were able to predict
224 potential presence of fecal contamination. However, the differences found between the
225 levels of *E. coli* of those samples positive and negative to the presence of foodborne
226 pathogen were less significant in the case of qPCR ($P < 0.01$) than plate count method (P
227 < 0.001).

228

229 2.2. Suitability of different *E. coli* enumeration methods to assess microbial quality 230 of irrigation water sources

231 Three different types of irrigation water were compared to assess if there were
232 differences in microbial quality. Independently of the enumeration method, SW showed
233 the lowest *E. coli* levels, which agreed with the expected results (**Fig. 4**). When *E. coli*
234 levels were quantified by plate count significant differences were found among the water
235 sources tested (**Fig. 4A**). However, when the qPCR *E. coli* was used, no significant
236 differences were obtained between RW-2 and RW-3 (**Fig. 4B**). Results on water samples
237 positive for the presence of pathogenic bacteria showed that only secondary RW-2
238 samples were positive after confirmation (**Table 1**). When samples of RW-2 were
239 evaluated, it was observed that only when qPCR was used positives samples for

240 pathogenic bacteria showed significantly higher *E. coli* levels than samples negative for
241 the presence of foodborne pathogens (Fig. 5).

242

243 3. Discussion

244 The use of *E. coli* as an indicator of fecal contamination has been proposed as a
245 good strategy to characterize microbial contamination of irrigation water (Park et al.,
246 2013; Castro-Ibañez et al., 2015b; Ceuppens et al., 2015). Recently, it has been reported
247 that a qPCR-based *E. coli* assay was the best indicator for bacterial pathogens in water
248 samples (Ferguson et al., 2012). *E. coli* levels quantified by qPCR assay in different
249 samples such as rainwater and municipal sewage sludge were always higher than those
250 obtained using cultivation-based techniques (Ahmed et al., 2012; van Frankenhuyzen et
251 al., 2013). In our study, qPCR *E. coli* counts of irrigation water samples were always
252 around 1.3 log units higher than those obtained by traditional plate counts. As previously
253 described, a strong correlation between *E. coli* levels was obtained using both
254 enumeration techniques (Gonzalez and Noble, 2014; Ahmed et al., 2012). In the case of
255 zucchini samples, *E. coli* levels quantified by plate count were always below the detection
256 limits while positive samples (median 2.64 log cells/g, IQR 2.46-3.05) were detected by
257 qPCR. This discrepancy observed between plate count and qPCR methods in water and
258 zucchini samples could be due to the presence of viable but not cultivable (VBNC)
259 bacteria. The presence of VBNC bacteria in irrigation water and plant tissue has been
260 previously demonstrated (Juhna et al., 2007; Moyle et al., 2013).

261 In most of the studies, enumeration of fecal indicators such as *E. coli* has been
262 traditionally performed using cultivation-based assays. However, other enumeration
263 techniques such as qPCR, have been reported as suitable to predict the potential presence
264 of enteric foodborne pathogens in environmental samples (i.e. groundwater) (Ferguson et

265 al., 2012; Truchado et al., 2016). Results obtained in the current study showed that high
266 concentrations of *E. coli* were well correlated with the presence of pathogens in irrigation
267 water including reclaimed water treated with secondary and tertiary processes when both
268 plate count and qPCR were used. In groundwater samples, Ferguson et al., (2012) found
269 a better correlation between fecal indicator determined by molecular techniques and the
270 presence of pathogens than by using MPN.

271 When the suitability of different enumeration methods to classify the microbial
272 quality of different irrigation water sources was carried out, it was observed that the
273 cultivable-based method was able to differentiate the microbial quality among the water
274 sources. However, using qPCR *E. coli* enumeration, no significant differences were
275 obtained between the two recycled water types, RW-2 and RW-3. One hypothesis could
276 be that qPCR assay as such, cannot distinguish between viable and dead cells, leading to
277 an overestimation of *E. coli* levels in RW-3. Tertiary recycled water implied an additional
278 treatment based on coagulation-flocculation, lamellar clarification, sand filtration and UV-
279 C light. The UV-C treatment might be able to reduce viable cells but not the genetic
280 marker densities in the water. Different attempts have been performed trying to avoid
281 false-positive results when qPCR is used. The most widespread strategy is the use of
282 DNA-dyes such as PMA, which allow the differentiation between viable and dead cells
283 (Truchado et al., 2016). This technique is based on the ability of PMA to penetrate into
284 the dead cells with compromised membrane integrity and in turn inhibit DNA
285 amplification by PCR following light-induce cross-linking (Nocker and Camper, 2009;
286 Varma et al., 2009; Fittipaldi, et al., 2011). However, UV-C treatments rely upon DNA
287 break-up of the bacterial cells without compromising membrane integrity (Li et al., 2014).
288 Samples positive for the presence of foodborne pathogens were only found in RW-2.
289 When *E. coli* levels of RW-2 were enumerated using both plate count and qPCR and

290 correlated with the presence/absence of pathogens, levels of qPCR *E. coli* were
291 significantly higher in samples positive for the presence of pathogenic microorganism
292 while no significant differences were detected by the plate count enumeration technique.
293

294 **4. Conclusions**

295 Results confirm the positive correlation between high concentration of generic *E.*
296 *coli*, as indicator bacteria of fecal contamination and the likelihood of finding pathogens
297 in irrigation water. Cultivable and qPCR *E. coli* enumeration techniques seem to be
298 accurate methodologies for enumeration of *E. coli* as an indicator to predict the presence
299 of pathogenic bacteria in different water sources. However, the suitability of the different
300 techniques to predict potential fecal contamination might be affected by the
301 characteristics of the irrigation water. qPCR *E. coli* enumeration method seems to be a
302 better technique when poor quality water is evaluated. However, the results obtained were
303 based in a sample size of n=108 and further studies should be performed using higher
304 sample size to confirm the suitability of both *E. coli* enumeration methods in other water
305 sources.

306

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315

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Table 1. Pathogen microorganisms in different water sources and in zucchini irrigated with different water sources.

Samples type*	<i>E. coli</i> O157:H7		Non-O157:H7 STEC		<i>Salmonella</i>	
	Genedisc®	Confirmed	Genedisc®	Confirmed	Genedisc®	Confirmed
Water						
RW-2	3/18	1/3	3/18	3/3	4/18	0/4
RW-3	0/18		0/18		2/18	0/2
SW	1/18	0/1	0/18		0/18	
Zucchini	Genedisc®	Confirmed	Genedisc®	Confirmed	Genedisc®	Confirmed
RW-2	0/9		0/9		0/9	
RW-3	0/9		0/9		1/9	0/1
SW	0/9		0/9		0/9	

* RW-2: Secondary reclaimed water; RW-3: Tertiary reclaimed water; SW: surface water

Table 2. Sequencing of 16S rRNA gene from suspected *E. coli* strains isolated from water samples.

Samples*	Closest relative microorganisms	% Identity	Accession number
RW-2-1	<i>Escherichia coli</i> O157:H7 strain WS4202	99	CP012802
RW-2-2	<i>Escherichia coli</i> O104:H4 strain C227-11	99	CP011331
RW-2-3	<i>Escherichia coli</i> O104:H4 strain C227-11	99	CP011331
RW-2-4	<i>Escherichia coli</i> O78 strain ACN002	99	CP007491.1

* RW-2: Secondary reclaimed water; RW-3: Tertiary reclaimed water; SW: surface water.

Figure Legends

Fig. 1. Boxplots representing cultivable (plate count) and molecular (qPCR) *E. coli* counts in irrigation water (log cfu or cells/100 mL) (A) and zucchini (log cells/g) (B). Box-plot with different letters indicates significant difference at $P < 0.05$.

Fig. 2. Scatter plot of cultivable *E. coli* vs molecular *E. coli* levels in different types of irrigation water (n= 81).

Fig. 3. Boxplots representing cultivable (plate count) and molecular (qPCR) *E. coli* counts in irrigation water (log cfu or cells/100 mL). *E. coli* samples separated into those with absence or presence of foodborne pathogenic bacteria. Box-plots labelled with different letters indicate significant difference at $P < 0.05$.

Fig. 4. Boxplots representing cultivable (plate count) (A) and molecular (qPCR) (B) *E. coli* levels (log cfu or cells/100 mL) in secondary reclaimed water (RW-2), tertiary reclaimed water (RW-3) and surface water (SW). Box-plots labelled with different letters indicate significant difference at $P < 0.05$.

Fig. 5. Boxplots representing cultivable (plate count) and molecular (qPCR) *E. coli* levels (log cfu or cells/100 mL) in secondary reclaimed water (RW-2). *E. coli* samples separated into those with absence or presence of foodborne pathogenic bacteria. Box-plots labelled with different letters indicate significant difference at $P < 0.05$.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

Fig. 3.

Fig. 4.

Fig. 5.

